

THEORETICAL REVIEW OF EVALUATING FOREIGN LANGUAGE KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS, AND COMPETENCE BASED ON CEFR AND OTHER INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAMS IN UZBEKISTAN

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***Annotation.** This article provides a theoretical review of methods and approaches for evaluating foreign language knowledge, skills, and competence in Uzbekistan based on the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) and other international assessment programs. It examines how global standards like TOEFL, IELTS, and other frameworks influence foreign language teaching and assessment practices in the country. The study highlights the alignment of Uzbekistan's language education policies with CEFR benchmarks and discusses the challenges and opportunities in implementing these international standards.*

***Keywords.** CEFR, foreign language assessment, language competence, international assessment programs, TOEFL, IELTS, language evaluation systems.*

Introduction. Regular assessment of acquired knowledge is a crucial component of the educational process [4: p36]. Pedagogical monitoring encompasses a system for teaching, instructing, and evaluating the results of instruction. This process allows for the identification of achievements and shortcomings. From an educational perspective, the assessment of students' knowledge, skills, and abilities involves identifying and measuring their lexical, grammatical, and pronunciation proficiency [6: p14].

Main part. Foreign languages are taught for practical, educational, developmental, and upbringing purposes, requiring mastery of both the technical and linguistic aspects for effective speech activity. According to one of the most prominent scholars in foreign language assessment and assessment literacy,

Kamola Muradkasimova, these methodological aspects are the subject of assessment. Methodological literature emphasizes testing knowledge, skills, and abilities; however, knowledge in foreign languages isn't specifically assessed, as it is integrated within the acquisition of skills. Therefore, skills are assessed, focusing on the level of lexical, grammatical, and pronunciation mastery, and their application in various speech activities. The assessment of abilities measures proficiency in using different types of speech activity as a means of communication. Assessment clarifies its purpose, objectives, and role. Once the nature of the assessment and the object of the assessment are defined, the organization of the assessment process itself becomes paramount. Clarifying concepts such as method, type, form, test, and rating is crucial in assessment methodology. However, contemporary approaches focus on developing communicative competencies, particularly lexical competence, a goal unattainable through tests alone. Therefore, Muradkasimova deemed it necessary to use the term "assessment" in her research [7: p40].

J. Jalolov notes that skill assessment involves knowledge and application of vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, and speech patterns in oral communication. Ability assessment, conversely, focuses on the mastery of various types of speech activity. For example, methods for assessing active vocabulary include constructing as many sentences as possible using given speech samples, and other similar tasks [5].

The study conducted by Rashidova F. establishes a foundation for defining and assessing language proficiency aligned with international standards, both during and upon completion of studies. The conceptual and methodological development of foreign language proficiency assessment within a continuous education system should aim to ensure and further optimize the compatibility between education systems and the demands of the market economy, a crucial aspect of this research. The need for and timeliness of effective research into a unified system for assessing foreign language proficiency, using English as an example, is

underscored by the current existence of numerous international assessment systems. This explains the interconnectedness of systems evaluating learners' language skills, such as the International English Language Testing System (IELTS), English tests for foreigners, and Cambridge University examinations for learners and teachers (Cambridge Exams).

The lack of a unified system for learning, teaching, and assessing foreign language proficiency at each stage of education is highly problematic [8: pp36-40]. Uzbekistan adopted a national system for certifying foreign language proficiency from 2014-2017, aligned with CEFR or Uz SES standards [1], which gained recognition across all educational levels in the country and subsequently internationally [2]. With the implementation of the CEFR, countries began aligning their assessment systems with the acquisition of four communicative language skills – listening, speaking, reading, and writing – allowing for the identification of the user's language proficiency level. The acquisition of these skills is part of a broader communicative competence. In 2022, the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan №73, “On the approval of the administrative regulations for the provision of state services for determining the level of foreign language proficiency” [3] was approved, and many positive changes have occurred. It is necessary to endorse the proposal to implement a generalized multi-level testing system for the B1, B2, and C1 levels, in addition to the existing procedure for conducting separate examinations at each level (A2, B1, B2, C1). This system aims to enhance the efficiency and convenience of the examination process.

Let's consider the Cambridge English Language Assessment (CEA), established by "Cambridge English Language Assessment," a commercial organization regulating CEFR requirements and other internationally recognized examination systems. One of the founders of CEFR, John Trim, notes that this assessment system should serve individuals regardless of location, occupation, or age; it should provide a sense of global recognition. Numerous examples demonstrate

how Cambridge English examinations embody and reflect CEFR in various forms, earning recognition from diverse communities and organizations, including educational institutions [9].

In conclusion, the implementation of internationally recognized assessment programs like CEFR, IELTS, and CEA in Uzbekistan's education system has played a significant role in achieving global standards in foreign language education.

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